

Economic and Financial Valuation of Companies using Linguistic Information Based on Expertons and 2-Tuple Linguistic Representation

Mendaña Cuervo, C.; López González, E.; Caño Alegre, C.; González Pérez, B.
Department of Management and Business Economy
University of León
Campus de Vegazana, s/n. E-24071 León (Spain)
E-mail: dde {cmc,elg,cca}@unileon.es

SUMMARY

The aim of this work is to analyse estimates of the economic and financial value of a company in environments of uncertainty, in which it is possible that can be obtained only through opinions expressed by experts. For such situations, a model will be proposed that allows processing of this information by means of linguistic labels, as opposed to its presentation in the form of precise numerical values. Additionally, consideration will be given to the possibility of representing this information by the use of linguistic 2-tuples, a methodology that allows operations with data provided in different domains of expression. Furthermore, in view of the good results obtained with the technique of expertons in problems involving the aggregation of judgements by experts, in this work a hybrid model will be set out that renders possible a joint application to the valuation of companies.

Keywords: Valuation of companies; uncertainty; linguistic information; aggregation algorithms; 2-tuple representations; expertons.

1. Introduction

In purchases, mergers, take-overs and so forth, for which it is necessary to establish a purchase price acceptable to all parties involved in the transaction, problems arise in respect of the valuation of businesses, especially in those cases where the information available is in the form of subjective views expressed by experts. In fact, in such circumstances it may not be feasible to set up any standardized criterion usable for every instance, since each operation is in itself different from all others. Hence, it is normally the case that the determination of the value of a business is bound up with a process of negotiation. It is true that mechanisms can be established to aid progress towards a joint agreement and that on many occasions these are based on the opinions sought from experts in the field who facilitate the finding of common ground on which the interested parties can negotiate until an agreement is reached that satisfies both sides.

In the circumstances mentioned above a need arises for tools allowing people to work with the uncertainty inherent in opinions expressed by individuals, normally defined in terms of linguistic values. Thus, this paper will offer an example of an application of the possibilities of a representation in the form of language 2-tuples to the valuation of businesses for which the information available is expressed as linguistic labels and in varying domains of expression. Similarly, and in view of the need to submit this information to processes of aggregation, consideration will be given to the feasibility of using this sort of representation in conjunction with the technique of expertons proposed by Professors Kaufmann and Gil Aluja

(1992). The results obtained will permit some final thoughts to be offered in the last section by way of a conclusion for this paper.

2. The problem of putting an economic and financial value on businesses in a context of uncertainty

The meaning given to the expression "worth of a business" depends on the position from which it is defined. Thus, it is possible to establish a worth for an enterprise in terms of the value set by shareholders and creditors on the rights they possess (shares, bonds and so forth), in this case taking account of the worth of elements on the liabilities side of the balance sheet, or in other words, the structure of the firm's financing. On the other hand, the worth assigned to an enterprise from the point of view of potential buyers or sellers of it concentrates on the value of the assets needed to generate profits and forecasts about the future evolution of these. In this latter case, any process of valuation will be subject to the need to agree some form of mechanism facilitating the processing of information which is subjective and in many cases qualitative in nature. This is because it is necessary to make estimates of amounts that relate to the future, as well as bringing into consideration the opinions of third parties about the likely future evolution of the business.

In the specialist literature a number of authors have offered a range of alternatives for carrying out a valuation process, among which the following are of note:

- Historical cost criterion. This basically considers the value of each asset to be the price for which it was purchased when acquired by the firm. It thus has clear drawbacks, in that it does not take into account the effects of inflation, technological progress and the like.
- Replacement cost criterion. This approach takes as its reference for estimating the value of all of the items on the asset side their current market price and their economic efficiency.
- Capitalized profit criterion. This starts from the premise that making profits is the prime aim of a firm, so that they form the basis for calculating its value. Thus, the valuation is performed by discounting the estimated profits for future periods by means of interest rates. It requires three variables to be determined: interest rates, likely profit for each period and timespan taken into consideration.

A process of valuation undertaken using the last criterion should yield a value greater than those carried out using the other two criteria. This difference is termed the goodwill, and to calculate it two principal approaches are used. The direct method consists of estimating both potential profits and normal income, determining the current value of the difference between them, and the indirect method involves working out the current value of estimated profits and deducting the base value.

Use of a capitalized profits criterion modified by the base value gives rise to what are termed mixed methods, among which are to be noted the German method, the Schmalenbach method and the Anglo-Saxon method. The German method attempts to avoid the drawbacks of the uncertainty of data relating to the future. For this purpose, given that there is a lack of appropriate techniques for handling such data, it opts for the reduction of the capitalized value to half the goodwill, with as justification the principle of prudence in valuations. In this way, it holds that:

$$V_e = V_s + \frac{1}{2} GW = V_e - \frac{1}{2} GW = V_e - \frac{1}{2} (V_e - V_s) = \frac{V_e + V_s}{2} \quad (1)$$

where V_e is the value of the firm, V_s is the base value, V_c is the capitalized value and GW is the goodwill ($V_c - V_s$).

In the expression (1) it may be observed that this method determines the value of the enterprise as an average of the capitalized value and the base value, hence considering that both types of valuation are of equal importance. For its part, the Anglo-Saxon method performs calculations by adding to the base value the whole amount of the goodwill. In consequence, both methods suffer from similar limitations, as all that differs from one to the other is the exact procedure for calculations. In the German method, the goodwill is obtained indirectly as the difference between the capitalized value and the base value; in the Anglo-Saxon method, it is determined directly as the current value of the difference between the expected profits and the normal income derivable from the base value. Hence, if i is the normal interest rate, the value of the enterprise would be given:

$$V_c = V_s + (B - iV_s) \frac{(1+i)^n - 1}{(1+i) \cdot i} \quad (2)$$

The expression above reflects the fact that the normal income, rather than being calculated on the base value, takes into account the worth of the business in the sense of what potential buyers would theoretically pay for it. In the case where the future estimated profits and interest rates differ from period to period, the value of the business would be given by:

$$V_c = V_s + (B_1 - i_1 V_s)(1+i_1)^{-1} + \dots + (B_n - i_n V_s)(1+i_1)^{-1} (1+i_2)^{-1} \dots (1+i_n)^{-1} \quad (3)$$

Nevertheless, calculations performed in this way have a number of drawbacks which must be kept in mind and, if possible, avoided to establish a valuation as close as feasible to the real state of affairs. Among these disadvantages is the fact that estimates both of interest rates and of expected future profits have to be made by experts, and so it is highly desirable to have a mechanism facilitating the collection and later aggregation of such information. In fact, the data available for this purpose cannot normally be obtained in a precise form as a quantitative measurement (a number), with it being easier to get it expressed by the experts in a qualitative form. In this case, the use of a linguistic approach works better than numeric approaches. Fuzzy language methodology is an approximation technique developed on the basis of the Theory of Fuzzy Subsets and representing qualitative aspects as linguistic values through the use of "linguistic variables".

3. The 2-tuple linguistic representation model

A model of representation based on pairs of values or 2-tuples was drawn up by Herrera and Martínez (2000, 2001) as a system valid for representing and handling language information. This model is grounded on the concept of symbol translation, which may be defined as follows: Let $S = \{S_0, \dots, S_g\}$ a set of language items and $\beta \in [0, g]$ a value obtained by a symbolic method operating with linguistic information. The symbolic translation of a language item s_i is a number lying in the range $[-0.5, +0.5)$ which shows the "difference in information" between an amount of information expressed by the value $\beta \in [0, g]$ obtained in a symbolic operation and i the nearest whole number value, $i \in \{0, \dots, g\}$, which indicates the pointer or index for the closest language label (s_i) in S . This representational model with the idea of symbolic translation at its heart uses as a basis for representation 2-tuples, (τ_i, α_i) where $\tau_i \in S$ and $\alpha_i \in [-0.5, 0.5)$, and τ_i is a language label and α_i is a number expressing the value of the distance from the original result β to the index of the closest linguistic label (τ_i)

in the set of language terms S , that is, its symbolic translation.

The use of the representation just explained requires each language label to be converted into its equivalent 2-tuple. For this purpose, if $s_i \in S$ is a linguistic item belonging to the set S of language terms, its representation as an equivalent 2-tuple is found through the function θ :

$$\begin{aligned} \theta: S &\rightarrow (S \times [-0.5, 0.5]) \\ \theta(s_i) &= (s_i, 0) / s_i \in S \end{aligned} \quad (4)$$

Likewise, from a numeric value β , $\beta \in [0, g]$, obtained through a symbol operation, it is possible to get the language 2-tuple expressing the information equivalent to β , by using the function:

$$\begin{aligned} \Delta: [0, g] &\rightarrow S \times [-0.5, 0.5] \\ \Delta(\beta) &= (s_i, \alpha), \text{ with } \begin{cases} s_i & i = \text{round}(\beta) \\ \alpha = \beta - i & \alpha \in [-0.5, 0.5]. \end{cases} \end{aligned} \quad (5)$$

where *round* is the usual rounding operator, s_i is the label with the subscript or index closest to β and α is the value of the symbol translation.

To apply it to the problem of setting a value on businesses, where there is a need to operate with information supplied by several experts, it is necessary to consider the capacity of this representational model offers for tackling the problem of aggregating opinions. On this point, it should be noted that the representation of information by means of linguistic 2-tuples has its own defined operators for aggregation, both symbolic operators extended for use with language 2-tuples and operators based on those for numerical aggregation (Herrera and Martínez, 2000). Nonetheless, as an outcome of the good results obtained from applying it jointly with the methodology of expertons (Mendaña Cuervo and López González, 2001), in this paper consideration is given to the usefulness of combined utilization of a representation based on linguistic 2-tuples and the theory of expertons. Similarly, in situations such as those arising in the valuation of businesses, where it is necessary to draw information from opinions put forward by individuals, it would seem logical to seek tools facilitating on the one hand the gathering of data by providing experts with the means to express themselves and on the other the aggregation of the information obtained in this way.

4. Hybrid model for valuing businesses with linguistic information through the application of Expertons and 2-tuples linguistics

As noted in section two, the various criteria for valuing enterprises require estimates to be made both of interest rates and of profits expected. In both cases the information refers to the future, and for this reason it is not common for there to be sure numerical data for a la valuation. This implies a need to have recourse to whatever opinions experts can provide about the future behaviour of these two variables. Thus, the process of obtaining information so as to establish the expected worth of a business makes it necessary to have mechanisms facilitating the expression of opinions concerning the estimates of these amounts. In consequence this paper allows for experts to state their views in language terms, so making it easy for each expert to choose the range of linguistic items felt most suitable for putting a value on this. Hence, an overview will next be given of the model put forward in this paper as applied to evaluating both interest rates and expected profits with a view to aid the process of valuing enterprises. Similarly, with the aim of giving a clearer understanding of the procedure described, an illustrative practical example will be offered for the two areas of study.

5.1 Estimating future interest rates

So as to determine the worth of a business, a process of estimating interest rates starts with an analysis of the ranges within which rates are expected to fluctuate during the periods being considered, so that they can act as a starting point for the negotiations between the parties involved in the matter. In the illustrative practical example being put forward here a three-year period has been taken for consideration, with the following ranges of interest rates being assumed: [0'04, 0'05], [0'045, 0'06] and [0'05, 0'06]. With a view to reaching consensus over the validity of this information, it is feasible to go to several experts (the practical example supposes 10 in all) and to get them to indicate how far they agree with these starting values. The request for people to give information, according to the views put forward in earlier sections, should be made in such a way that each person can express it in whatever terms are most normal for that expert. In other words, the domain of expression should not be imposed, but rather every effort should be made to aid in the gathering of information regardless of the domain chosen by each expert. For illustrative purposes, in solving the problem the assumption is made that the experts will lay out their opinions using the language set they find easiest to use among the following:

$$S^5 = \{VH, H, M, L, VL\}; S^7 = \{VH, QH, H, M, L, QL, VL\}; S^9 = \{PC, VH, QH, H, M, L, QL, VL, PN\}. \quad (6)$$

where the superscript indicates the number of labels in the language set, and where the associated meanings are as follows:

$S^5 = \{VH=Very_High, H=High, M=Middling, L=Low, VL=Very_Low\}$

$S^7 = \{VH=Very_High, QH=Quite_High, H=High, M=Middling, L=Low, QL=Quite_Low, VL=Very_Low\}$

$S^9 = \{PC=Practically_Certain, VH=Very_High, QH=Quite_High, H=High, M=Middling, L=Low, QL=Quite_Low, VL=Very_Low, PN=Practically_Nil\}$

Despite the above, it is possible for expert opinions not to match exactly any of the labels lists given, with the possibility that an answer might straddle a pair of the labels in any given domain. On this basis, for illustrative purposes it is supposed that the information provided by the experts is as set out in Table 1.

Expert	[0'04, 0'05]	[0'045, 0'06]	[0'05, 0'06]	Domain
e_1	H - VH	VH	L - M	S^5
e_2	H - QH	H - VH	VL - M	S^7
e_3	QH	PC	PN - L	S^9
e_4	H	VH - PC	QL - M	S^9
e_5	H - VH	H - VH	L	S^5
e_6	VH	H	VL - L	S^5
e_7	PC	H - VH	QL - M	S^9
e_8	H - VH	H - QH	H - VH	S^9
e_9	VH	QL - L	H - QH	S^7
e_{10}	PN - VL	H - QH	QH - PC	S^9

Table 1.- Valuations in language terms supplied by experts

Consequently, the data available for making a decision are expressed as multi-textured language information, and this is the reason that the first thing to be done is to unify this infor-

mation into a single domain of expression. As commented in section 4.1, the method proposed to solve this problem in the current paper is that of language hierarchies as put forward by Herrera and Martínez (2000). In the situation sketched above the domains would be defined as follows:

$$\begin{array}{cccccc}
 e_1 & l(1,5) & e_2 & l(2,7) & e_3 & l(3,9) & e_4 & l(3,9) & e_5 & l(1,5) \\
 e_6 & l(1,5) & e_7 & l(3,9) & e_8 & l(3,9) & e_9 & l(2,7) & e_{10} & l(3,9)
 \end{array} \quad (7)$$

so that the valuations established by each of the experts can be represented on the basis of which domain is utilized as shown in Table 2.

The first step required is a normalization of the valuations established by the experts. For this it is necessary to determine what set of language items is to be used as the basis for unifying the information. For practical reasons, given that the majority of the experts in the example use the domain $l(3,9)$, this will be the one utilized as a reference for unification purposes, although it would be perfectly possible to select any other whatsoever.

Expert	[0'04, 0'05]	[0'045, 0'06]	[0'05, 0'06]
e_1	$S_3^s - S_4^s$	S_4^s	$S_1^s - S_2^s$
e_2	$S_4^- - S_3^s$	$S_4^- - S_6^-$	$S_0^s - S_3^-$
e_3	S_6^y	S_8^y	$S_0^y - S_3^y$
e_4	S_5^y	$S_7^y - S_8^y$	$S_2^y - S_4^y$
e_5	$S_3^s - S_4^s$	$S_3^s - S_4^s$	S_1^s
e_6	S_4^s	S_3^s	$S_0^s - S_1^s$
e_7	S_8^y	$S_5^y - S_7^y$	$S_2^y - S_4^y$
e_8	$S_5^y - S_7^y$	$S_5^y - S_6^y$	$S_5^y - S_7^y$
e_9	S_6^s	$S_1^s - S_2^-$	$S_4^s - S_3^-$
e_{10}	$S_0^y - S_1^y$	$S_5^y - S_6^y$	$S_6^y - S_8^y$

Table 2.- Linguistic valuations represented in each domain

Thus, as an illustration, the unification of the expressions of the first expert (e_1) is shown, where an application of the transformation function would work as follows:

$$\text{Example: for H} \quad = \quad (s_3^s, 0) \rightarrow TF_3^1 (s_3^s, 0) = \Delta^1 \left(\frac{\Delta(s_3^s, 0) \cdot (9-1)}{(5-1)} \right) = \Delta^1 (6) = (s_6^y, 0) \quad (8)$$

In a similar way the information provided by the remaining experts would be normalized, yielding the unified values in the chosen domain of expression, reflected in Table 3.

Expert	[0'04, 0'05]	[0'045, 0'06]	[0'05, 0'06]
e_1	$(S_6^y, 0) - (S_8^y, 0)$	$(S_8^y, 0)$	$(S_2^y, 0) - (S_7^y, 0)$
e_2	$(S_3^y, 0'33) - (S_7^y, -0'33)$	$(S_3^y, 0'33) - (S_8^y, 0)$	$(S_0^y, 0) - (S_4^y, 0)$
e_3	$(S_6^y, 0)$	$(S_8^y, 0)$	$(S_0^y, 0) - (S_3^y, 0)$
e_4	$(S_5^y, 0)$	$(S_7^y, 0) - (S_8^y, 0)$	$(S_2^y, 0) - (S_4^y, 0)$
e_5	$(S_6^y, 0) - (S_8^y, 0)$	$(S_6^y, 0) - (S_8^y, 0)$	$(S_2^y, 0)$
e_6	$(S_8^y, 0)$	$(S_6^y, 0)$	$(S_0^y, 0) - (S_2^y, 0)$
e_7	$(S_8^y, 0)$	$(S_5^y, 0) - (S_7^y, 0)$	$(S_2^y, 0) - (S_4^y, 0)$
e_8	$(S_5^y, 0) - (S_7^y, 0)$	$(S_5^y, 0) - (S_6^y, 0)$	$(S_5^y, 0) - (S_7^y, 0)$
e_9	$(S_8^y, 0)$	$(S_7^y, 0'33) - (S_3^y, -0'33)$	$(S_3^y, 0'33) - (S_7^y, -0'33)$
e_{10}	$(S_0^y, 0) - (S_1^y, 0)$	$(S_3^y, 0) - (S_6^y, 0)$	$(S_6^y, 0) - (S_8^y, 0)$

Table 3.-- Unified values for the linguistic evaluations

Once the information represented as language 2-tuples has been unified into a single domain of expression, it is possible to proceed to a process of aggregation for these data, consisting of finding a value to represent the set of values (set of opinions) it is desired to aggregate. The result of such a process applied to a set of 2-tuples will itself be a 2-tuple, independently of the criteria selected for aggregating. In this paper the option has been to apply the method of expertons (Kaufmann and Gil Aluja, 1993), using the various linguistic 2-tuples obtained from the process of normalization and unification of the multi-textured information set out in Table 3 above. From these data it is possible to obtain the related statistics and the expertons that figure in Table 4 for each of the 2-tuples obtained.

[0'04, 0'05]		[0'045, 0'06]		[0'05, 0'06]	
Statistic	Experton	Statistic	Experton	Statistic	Experton
$(S_0^y, 0)$	1 0 0'9 1'0	$(S_0^y, 0)$	0 0 1'0 1'0	$(S_0^y, 0)$	3 0 0'7 1'0
$(S_1^y, 0)$	0 1 0'9 1'0	$(S_1^y, 0)$	0 0 1'0 1'0	$(S_1^y, 0)$	0 0 0'7 1'0
$(S_2^y, 0)$	0 0 0'9 0'9	$(S_1^y, 0'33)$	1 0 1'0 1'0	$(S_2^y, 0)$	4 2 0'7 1'0
$(S_3^y, 0)$	0 0 0'9 0'9	$(S_2^y, 0)$	0 0 0'9 1'0	$(S_3^y, 0)$	0 1 0'3 0'8
$(S_4^y, 0)$	0 0 0'9 0'9	$(S_3^y, -0'33)$	0 1 0'9 1'0	$(S_4^y, 0)$	0 4 0'3 0'7
$(S_5^y, 0)$	2 1 0'9 0'9	$(S_3^y, 0)$	0 0 0'9 0'9	$(S_5^y, 0)$	1 0 0'3 0'3
$(S_5^y, 0'33)$	1 0 0'7 0'8	$(S_4^y, 0)$	0 0 0'9 0'9	$(S_5^y, 0'33)$	1 0 0'2 0'3
$(S_6^y, 0)$	3 1 0'6 0'8	$(S_5^y, 0)$	3 0 0'9 0'9	$(S_6^y, 0)$	1 0 0'1 0'3
$(S_7^y, -0'33)$	0 1 0'3 0'7	$(S_5^y, 0'33)$	1 0 0'6 0'9	$(S_7^y, -0'33)$	0 1 0'0 0'3
$(S_7^y, 0)$	0 1 0'3 0'6	$(S_6^y, 0)$	2 3 0'5 0'9	$(S_7^y, 0)$	0 1 0'0 0'2
$(S_8^y, 0)$	3 5 0'3 0'5	$(S_7^y, 0)$	1 1 0'3 0'6	$(S_8^y, 0)$	0 1 0'0 0'1
		$(S_8^y, 0)$	2 5 0'2 0'5		

Table 4.-- Statistics and Expertons

From the information given above it is feasible to determine the R+ expertons, proceeding as reflected in Table 5 for the first period. From the values yielded it is possible to calculate the mathematical expectation, which will be:

$$\hat{i}_1 = [0'04670, 0'04800] \quad \hat{i}_2 = [0'05605, 0'05809] \quad \hat{i}_3 = [0'05260, 0'05500] \quad (9)$$

This permits the establishment of an aggregate opinion for the experts that will offer an estimate for interest rates that is tighter than those initially considered. If it were felt necessary to proceed to parameterize the data supplied by the experts, because of the drawbacks posed by this methodology in respect of transferring the intervals obtained up to the ends of the scale, this could be done, taking into account the parameterized identification by Sugeno (1974) as:

$$i^{(\lambda)} = \frac{i}{1 + (1-i)\lambda}, \quad \lambda \in]-1, \infty) \quad (10)$$

0'04 + (0'05 - 0'04) (·)	$(S_0^y, 0)$	0'90 1'00	=	$(S_0^y, 0)$	0'049 0'050
	$(S_1^y, 0)$	0'90 1'00		$(S_1^y, 0)$	0'049 0'050
	$(S_2^y, 0)$	0'90 0'90		$(S_2^y, 0)$	0'049 0'049
	$(S_3^y, 0)$	0'90 0'90		$(S_3^y, 0)$	0'049 0'049
	$(S_4^y, 0)$	0'90 0'90		$(S_4^y, 0)$	0'049 0'049
	$(S_5^y, 0)$	0'90 0'90		$(S_5^y, 0)$	0'049 0'049
	$(S_5^y, 0'33)$	0'70 0'80		$(S_5^y, 0'33)$	0'047 0'048
	$(S_6^y, 0)$	0'06 0'80		$(S_6^y, 0)$	0'046 0'048
	$(S_7^y, -0'33)$	0'30 0'70		$(S_7^y, -0'33)$	0'043 0'047
	$(S_7^y, 0)$	0'30 0'60		$(S_7^y, 0)$	0'043 0'046
	$(S_8^y, 0)$	0'30 0'50		$(S_8^y, 0)$	0'043 0'045
		Experton			R ⁺ -experton

Table 5.- R+ Expertons for the first period

The operations noted above require the value of the parameter λ to be determined. For the purposes of illustration it is estimated as that it will be appropriate to consider $\lambda \in [0, 1]$. Specifically, to resolve the example a value of $\lambda = 0'5$ is established. Parameterization to obtain the mathematical expectation $\varepsilon(i^{(\lambda=0'5)})$ will be carried out level by level for each 2-tuple yielded by the experton, so that for the first period the result will be in Table 6.

$(S_0^p, 0)$	0'90	1'00	=	$(S_0^p, 0)$	0'857	1'000
$(S_1^p, 0)$	0'90	1'00		$(S_1^p, 0)$	0'857	1'000
$(S_2^p, 0)$	0'90	0'90		$(S_2^p, 0)$	0'857	0'857
$(S_3^p, 0)$	0'90	0'90		$(S_3^p, 0)$	0'857	0'857
$(S_4^p, 0)$	0'90	0'90		$(S_4^p, 0)$	0'857	0'857
$(S_5^p, 0)$	0'90	0'90		$(S_5^p, 0)$	0'857	0'857
$(S_5^p, 0'33)$	0'70	0'80		$(S_5^p, 0'33)$	0'609	0'727
$(S_6^p, 0)$	0'06	0'80		$(S_6^p, 0)$	0'500	0'727
$(S_7^p, -0'33)$	0'30	0'70		$(S_7^p, -0'33)$	0'222	0'609
$(S_8^p, 0)$	0'30	0'60		$(S_8^p, 0)$	0'222	0'500
$(S_8^p, 0)$	0'30	0'50		$(S_8^p, 0)$	0'222	0'400
Experton				R*-experton		

Table 6.— Parameterization of the data for the first period

The mathematical expectation emerging from the experton using these parameters will equal [0'6061, 0'7392]. Hence, the interest relating to this first period under consideration can be estimated as follows:

$$E(i^{(\lambda=0'5)}) = 0'04 + (0'05 - 0'04)(\cdot) [0'6061, 0'7392] = [0'04606, 0'04739] \quad (11)$$

Working in similar fashion for the interest rates of the two subsequent periods the following results are obtained for the three ranges: [0'04606, 0'04739], [0'05530, 0'05753], [0'05210, 0'05444].

5.2 Estimating future profits

The process of setting a valuation on a business, as indicated above, requires the establishment of values on which the buyers and sellers can agree in respect of the profits that it may be possible to earn over the periods under consideration for this purpose. To do this, the starting point should be the choice of intervals for quantifying profits that can serve as a framework for requesting opinions from experts in the field selected by both the sellers and the buyers. To meet the operational requirements for the resolution of the example, the following intervals were used for indicating possible profits for the three periods under analysis:

$$B_{-1} = [4.000, 6.000] \quad B_{-2} = [3.000, 6.000] \quad B_{-3} = [2.000, 5.000] \quad (12)$$

On the basis of the estimates given above, it is appropriate to request the collaboration of a group of experts, specifically here as in example 5 experts, who will express their views in the shape of linguistic evaluations. With the object of facilitating the gathering of this information, each expert is permitted to state an opinion using whatever range or domain of language is most feasible. In this way, assuming the opinions are as shown in Table 7, it is possible, to represent them as a function of the domain used by each of the experts, as laid in Table 7 too.

Buyers		[4000, 6000]	[3000, 6000]	[2000, 5000]
e_1	S^s	M-H $(S_2^s, 0) - (S_3^s, 0)$	L-M $(S_1^s, 0) - (S_2^s, 0)$	L-M $(S_1^s, 0) - (S_2^s, 0)$
e_2	S^-	QL-M $(S_1^7, 0) - (S_2^7, 0)$	M-QH $(S_3^7, 0) - (S_2^7, 0)$	VL-M $(S_0^7, 0) - (S_3^7, 0)$
e_3	S^y	H $(S_5^y, 0)$	VL-QL $(S_1^y, 0) - (S_2^y, 0)$	PN-L $(S_0^y, 0) - (S_3^y, 0)$
e_4	S^y	H $(S_5^y, 0)$	H-QH $(S_5^y, 0) - (S_6^y, 0)$	QL-M $(S_2^y, 0) - (S_3^y, 0)$
e_5	S^s	L-M $(S_1^s, 0) - (S_2^s, 0)$	M-H $(S_2^s, 0) - (S_3^s, 0)$	L $(S_1^s, 0)$

Vendors		[4000, 6000]	[3000, 6000]	[2000, 5000]
e_1	S^-	QH-VH $(S_2^7, 0) - (S_6^7, 0)$	M-H $(S_3^7, 0) - (S_4^7, 0)$	H-QH $(S_4^7, 0) - (S_5^7, 0)$
e_2	S^y	M-QH $(S_4^y, 0) - (S_6^y, 0)$	VH-PC $(S_7^y, 0) - (S_8^y, 0)$	L-M $(S_3^y, 0) - (S_4^y, 0)$
e_3	S^s	M-H $(S_2^s, 0) - (S_3^s, 0)$	H $(S_3^s, 0)$	L-M $(S_1^s, 0) - (S_2^s, 0)$
e_4	S^s	L-H $(S_1^s, 0) - (S_2^s, 0)$	L-M $(S_1^s, 0) - (S_2^s, 0)$	L-H $(S_1^s, 0) - (S_2^s, 0)$
e_5	S^y	H-QH $(S_5^y, 0) - (S_6^y, 0)$	VH-PC $(S_7^y, 0) - (S_8^y, 0)$	QH-VH $(S_6^y, 0) - (S_7^y, 0)$

Table 7.- Linguistic valuations and 2-tuple representation for future profits as supplied by the experts

The process of standardizing or normalizing the information given above into a single domain of expression will be carried out in a similar fashion to what was described in the previous section, utilizing the domain $I(3,9)$, and yielding the result shown in Table 8.

Buyers	[4000, 6000]	[3000, 6000]	[2000, 5000]
e_1	$(S_2^y, 0) - (S_6^y, 0)$	$(S_2^y, 0) - (S_4^y, 0)$	$(S_2^y, 0) - (S_4^y, 0)$
e_2	$(S_1^y, 0'33) - (S_2^y, 0)$	$(S_1^y, 0) - (S_2^y, -0'33)$	$(S_0^y, 0) - (S_3^y, 0)$
e_3	$(S_5^y, 0)$	$(S_1^y, 0) - (S_2^y, 0)$	$(S_0^y, 0) - (S_3^y, 0)$
e_4	$(S_5^y, 0)$	$(S_3^y, 0) - (S_6^y, 0)$	$(S_2^y, 0) - (S_3^y, 0)$
e_5	$(S_2^y, 0) - (S_4^y, 0)$	$(S_4^y, 0) - (S_6^y, 0)$	$(S_2^y, 0)$

Vendors	[4000, 6000]	[3000, 6000]	[2000, 5000]
e_1	$(S_7^y, -0'33) - (S_8^y, 0)$	$(S_4^y, 0) - (S_5^y, 0'33)$	$(S_3^y, 0'33) - (S_7^y, -0'33)$
e_2	$(S_4^y, 0) - (S_6^y, 0)$	$(S_7^y, 0) - (S_8^y, 0)$	$(S_3^y, 0) - (S_4^y, 0)$
e_3	$(S_4^y, 0) - (S_6^y, 0)$	$(S_6^y, 0)$	$(S_2^y, 0) - (S_3^y, 0)$
e_4	$(S_2^y, 0) - (S_6^y, 0)$	$(S_2^y, 0) - (S_4^y, 0)$	$(S_2^y, 0) - (S_6^y, 0)$
e_5	$(S_5^y, 0) - (S_6^y, 0)$	$(S_7^y, 0) - (S_8^y, 0)$	$(S_6^y, 0) - (S_7^y, 0)$

Table 8.- Standardized language valuations

Thereafter, this unified information needs to be aggregated, giving a value which represents the set of opinions gleaned from the various experts. For this purpose, aggregation is performed by using the same methods applied in the case of the estimation of interest rates as a function of expert opinions.

Thus, from the data laid out in Table 8 it will be possible to establish the statistics corresponding to the opinions of the buyers' and of the sellers' experts and the expertons for each of the 2-tuples obtained as shown in Table 9 for purchaser's.

[4000, 6000]				[3000, 6000]				[2000, 5000]						
Statistic		Experton		Statistic		Experton		Statistic		Experton				
$(S_0^y, 0)$	0	0	1'00	1'00	$(S_0^y, 0)$	0	0	1'00	1'00	$(S_0^y, 0)$	2	0	0'60	1'00
$(S_1^y, 0)$	0	0	1'00	1'00	$(S_1^y, 0)$	1	0	1'00	1'00	$(S_1^y, 0)$	0	0	0'60	1'00
$(S_1^y, 0'33)$	1	0	1'00	1'00	$(S_2^y, 0)$	1	1	0'80	1'00	$(S_2^y, 0)$	3	1	0'60	1'00
$(S_2^y, 0)$	1	0	0'80	1'00	$(S_3^y, 0)$	0	0	0'60	0'80	$(S_3^y, 0)$	0	1	0'00	0'80
$(S_3^y, 0)$	0	0	0'60	1'00	$(S_4^y, 0)$	2	1	0'60	0'80	$(S_4^y, 0)$	0	3	0'00	0'60
$(S_4^y, 0)$	1	2	0'60	1'00	$(S_5^y, 0)$	1	0	0'20	0'60	$(S_5^y, 0)$	0	0	0'00	0'00
$(S_5^y, 0)$	2	2	0'40	0'60	$(S_6^y, 0)$	0	2	0'00	0'60	$(S_6^y, 0)$	0	0	0'00	0'00
$(S_6^y, 0)$	0	1	0'00	0'20	$(S_7^y, -0'33)$	0	1	0'00	0'20	$(S_7^y, 0)$	0	0	0'00	0'00
$(S_7^y, 0)$	0	0	0'00	0'00	$(S_7^y, 0)$	0	0	0'00	0'00	$(S_8^y, 0)$	0	0	0'00	0'00
$(S_8^y, 0)$	0	0	0'00	0'00	$(S_8^y, 0)$	0	0	0'00	0'00					

Table 9.- Statistics and expertons for purchasers' opinions

The information given above permits the R^+ expertons to be determined, although in order not to engage in repetition of the calculations, this has been done only for those operations corresponding to the first period for both buyers and sellers. The specific results obtained for the purchasers are those in Table 10. For the vendors the operations are similar.

$4.000 + (6.000 - 4.000)(\cdot)$	$(S_0^y, 0)$	1'00	1'00	=	$(S_0^y, 0)$	6.000	6.000
	$(S_1^y, 0)$	1'00	1'00		$(S_1^y, 0)$	6.000	6.000
	$(S_1^y, 0'33)$	1'00	1'00		$(S_1^y, 0'33)$	6.000	6.000
	$(S_2^y, 0)$	0'80	1'00		$(S_2^y, 0)$	5.600	6.000
	$(S_3^y, 0)$	0'60	1'00		$(S_3^y, 0)$	5.200	6.000
	$(S_4^y, 0)$	0'60	1'00		$(S_4^y, 0)$	5.200	6.000
	$(S_5^y, 0)$	0'40	0'60		$(S_5^y, 0)$	4.800	5.200
	$(S_6^y, 0)$	0'00	0'20		$(S_6^y, 0)$	4.000	4.400
	$(S_7^y, 0)$	0'00	0'00		$(S_7^y, 0)$	4.000	4.000
	$(S_8^y, 0)$	0'00	0'00		$(S_8^y, 0)$	4.000	4.000
	Experton			R^+ -experton			

Table 10. R^+ Expertons for purchasers

The mathematical expectations of the expertons above are $[0'489, 0'644]$ and $[0'489, 0'733]$ respectively, so that the following holds:

$$\varepsilon \left(B_{-1}^{(I)} \right) = 4.000 + (6.000 - 4.000)(\cdot) [0'489, 0'644] = [4.978, 5.289]; \quad \varepsilon \left(B_{-1}^{(V)} \right) = [4.978, 5.467] \quad (13)$$

For the remaining periods, the mathematical expectations of the purchasers' expertons are $[0'356, 0'556]$ and $[0'150, 0'425]$ and for the vendors' $[0'644, 0'778]$ and $[0'400, 0'640]$, which permits the following operation to be performed:

$$\varepsilon \left(B_{-2}^{(I)} \right) = 3.000 + (6.000 - 3.000)(\cdot) [0'356, 0'556] = [4.067, 4.667]; \quad \varepsilon \left(B_{-2}^{(V)} \right) = [4.933, 5.333] \quad (14)$$

$$\varepsilon\left(\underset{-3}{B}^{(C)}\right) = 2.000 + (5.000 - 2.000)(\cdot)[0'150, 0'425] = [2.450, 3.275]; \quad \varepsilon\left(\underset{-3}{B}^{(V)}\right) = [3.200, 3.920]$$

The procedures noted above allow values to be obtained which bring buyers' and sellers' opinions closer together, reducing the distance between the extremes of the intervals being proposed. Thus, as an initial approach for the first period, the aggregated opinion of the purchasers' experts sets a minimum figure of 4.978 which in this case actually coincides with the value expressed on the sellers' side. For their part, the vendors fix an upper valuation at 5.467, so that a new interval [4.978, 5.467] would emerge, reflecting all the expert opinions expressed. Hence, this process serves to provide a meeting point to act as the basis of the process of negotiations, although there might be some requirement for further expert views on the interval obtained. In this case, a similar procedure to that carried out with the initial intervals would be undertaken, permitting further reductions in the level of uncertainty through the decreased base for the interval emerging. Likewise, if it were felt necessary to translate the result obtained it would be possible to carry out parameterization, in a similar fashion to what was done in the case of the interest rates.

Despite all this, to make resolution of the example being considered here easier, the results deriving from the first procedure will be taken as valid. This information will thus be used in the process of calculating the worth of the business.

5.3 Calculation of the total worth of the business

The first section of this paper established the formula (1) as the basis for estimating the worth of a business.

This formulation can be simplified with the following nomenclature:

$$I_1^{-1} = (1+i_1)^{-1}; \quad I_2^{-1} = (1+i_1)^{-1} (1+i_2)^{-1}; \quad I_3^{-1} = (1+i_1)^{-1} (1+i_2)^{-1} (1+i_3)^{-1} \quad (15)$$

permitting reformulation of the expression for the worth of the enterprise in this way:

$$V_e = \frac{V_s + B_1 \cdot I_1^{-1} + B_2 \cdot I_2^{-1} + B_3 \cdot I_3^{-1}}{1 + i_1 \cdot I_1^{-1} + i_2 \cdot I_2^{-1} + i_3 \cdot I_3^{-1}} \quad (16)$$

Hence, to establish the worth of the business it is essential to have information about the base value (V_s), which may be determined in accordance with commonly accepted criteria. In any case this information could also be determined in uncertain or fuzzy terms, by means of an interval or range fixing the possible value assigned. Nonetheless, with the aim of not repeating calculations, for the purposes of the illustration it is assumed that the value in question is known and accepted to be an amount of 3.000 of the currency units being used. In a similar manner, the information available for the purpose of carrying out an estimation of the worth of the business is taken to be the following:

$$\begin{array}{lll} V_s = 3.000 & & \\ i_{-1} = [0'04606, 0'04739] & i_{-2} = [0'05530, 0'05753] & i_{-3} = [0'05210, 0'05444] \\ B_{-1} = [4.978, 5.467] & B_{-2} = [4.067, 5.333] & B_{-3} = [2.450, 3.920] \end{array} \quad (17)$$

Information concerning interest rates yields the corresponding current value weightings to be used (first period):

$$\left(I(+)_i \right)^{-1} = (I(+)[0'04606, 0'04739])^{-1} = \left[\frac{1}{1'04739}, \frac{1}{1'04606} \right] = [0'9548, 0'9560] \quad (18)$$

and this allows establishment of: $I^{-1} = \left(I(+)_i \right)^{-1} = [0'9548, 0'9560]$

The process of getting the interest rates and the adjusted profit figures for each of the periods in the numerical example is performed on the basis of the calculations listed below:

$$\begin{aligned} B_{-1}(\cdot)I^{-1} &= [4.978, 5.467](\cdot)[0'9548, 0'9560] = [4.753, 5.226]; & B_{-2}(\cdot)I^{-1} &= [3.671, 4.831]; & B_{-3}(\cdot)I^{-1} &= [2.098, 3.375] \\ i_{-1}(\cdot)I^{-1} &= [0'04606, 0'04739](\cdot)[0'9548, 0'9560] = [0'0440, 0'0453]; & i_{-2}(\cdot)I^{-1} &= [0'0499, 0'0521]; & i_{-3}(\cdot)I^{-1} &= [0'0446, 0'0469] \end{aligned}$$

Thus, by replacements in the formula, a final worth can be fixed for the business, given the values used in the example, in terms of the calculations for it established in this work:

$$V_e = \frac{3.000(+)[10.522, 13.432]}{I(+)[0'1385, 0'1443]} = \left[\frac{13.522}{1'1443}, \frac{16.432}{1'1385} \right] = [11.817, 14.433] \quad (19)$$

The result noted above permits it to be stated that the profit will not be less than 11.817 nor greater than 14.433 of the currency units in use. The size of the interval would be a matter for negotiation between the parties. If it were considered necessary to achieve an even smaller degree of uncertainty, it would be possible to have resort to further, independent, expert opinions, until the range of uncertainty can be accepted by both purchasers and vendors.

5. Conclusions

In the first place, the results emerging in this paper allow it to be stated that a representation in the form of 2-tuples for handling linguistic information is shown to be valid. Secondly, they demonstrate the advantages of this sort of representation, as opposed to models based on the principle of extension and symbolic models, when it comes to representing solutions coming from multi-textured contexts in the original domain of expression chosen by the experts or others supplying information for use in a decision-making process. Moreover, the practical example worked out permits recognition of the validity of the expertons technique used in conjunction with a representation in the form of language 2-tuples, when compared with the information aggregation operators traditionally employed on this sort of representation.

In an application to the problem of valuing businesses, joint use of the two techniques allows a treatment of the information supplied by the experts from both of the sides (purchasers and vendors) that may facilitate a process of consensus for this kind of operations. This is because it involves modifying the initial information as little as possible and attempting to facilitate the acquisition of this sort of information in natural language as used by humans.

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